

Agronomic characteristics

A possible donor for use in breeding monsoon rice

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Analysis of certain data from the All India Coordinated Rice Variety Trials indicates various degrees of photoperiod sensitivity in several semidwarfs derived from TKM 6. A variety's photoperiod sensitivity can be determined from its flowering behavior with different sowing times at one site or with simultaneous sowings at different latitudes if temperature effects are minimized. Data were selected from the Uniform Variety Trials (UVT) of 1974–75 (see table). In UVT-1, five TKM 6 derivatives with comparable sowing times flowered 23 days earlier, on the average, at Garikapadu (18°N) than at Nagina (26°N). They also flowered more quickly in a September-planted trial than in a June-planted trial at Pattambi (11°N).

In UVT-2, two TKM 6 derivatives flowered 25 days earlier at Coimbatore (11°N) than at Gurdaspur (31°N), while photoperiod-insensitive Jaya flowered at nearly the same times. In a late-planted trial at Warangal, they flowered 23 and 31 days earlier than in the early-planted trial, while Jaya flowered at similar times in both trials.

TKM 6 and IR8 or TN1, the parents of the tested varieties, are photoperiod insensitive; there may be complementary gene action, or one of the parents may possess a hypostatic gene for photoperiod sensitivity. Since the results described here are not found in crosses of IR8 or TN1 with other insensitive varieties, it is presumed that TKM 6 contributed to the expression of photoperiod sensitivity that is being observed. Perhaps TKM 6 harbors a gene for photoperiod sensitivity along with an inhibitor gene. TKM 6 owes its origin to the photoperiod-sensitive variety GEB 24. Discrepant flowering behavior has also been noted in other TKM 6 derivative semidwarfs like IR20, Cauvery, and CR 44-1.

A photoperiod-sensitive gene in TKM 6 would have significant implications, because the variety can be an effective donor in breeding for monsoon rices. TKM 6 can contribute good grain quality and a general field tolerance to diseases and pests that is

Relation of flowering times of some semidwarf derivatives of TKM 6 to latitude and sowing time, AICRIP Uniform Variety Trials (UVT), 1974–75^a.

Location	Latitude	Sowing date	Flowering time (days after sowing)				
			UVT-1				
			<i>IET 2813</i>	<i>IET 2830</i>	<i>IET 2845</i>	<i>IET 3127</i>	<i>Ratna</i>
Nagina	26°N	June 29	123	123	120	110	112
Garikapadu	18°N	July 2	95	100	95	88	95
Pattambi	11°N	June 13	85	90	85	85	85
Pattambi	11°N	Sept. 26	75	70	72	74	72
			UVT-2				
			<i>IET 2656</i>	<i>IET 2815</i>		<i>Jaya</i>	
Gurdaspur	31°N	June 16	125	119		104	
Coimbatore	11°N	June 14	100	93		102	
Warangal	18°N	June 17	113	115		100	
Warangal	18°N	Aug. 14	90	84		103	

^aAll varieties, except Jaya, are TKM 6 derivatives.

important in monsoon rices. The varieties described here have only moderate photoperiod sensitivity since selection pressure was not applied for the photoperiod sensitivity attribute *per se*.

Semidwarf and intermediate-height progenies of TKM 6 with higher degrees of photoperiod sensitivity can be found. Genetic studies and breeding programs are underway in an attempt to develop improved photoperiod-sensitive monsoon rices.

Disease resistance

Variation in response of some rice varieties to infection by bacterial blight

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During screening trials of rice for bacterial leaf blight *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson induced by clip inoculation, it was noted that some rices varied greatly in response to infection. To examine the consistency in infection response, some released and still-to-be-released rice varieties were subjected to field trials during kharif of 1973, 1974, and 1975 at the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah.

Disease responses in different years varied. The natural bacterial leaf blight pressure was higher in 1973 than in the

two succeeding years. The conditions for disease development might have been favorable in 1973, resulting in higher disease incidence in the inoculated plot in that year than in 1974 and 1975. Comparison of the data for 1973 with those for 1974 and 1975 reveals wide variations in disease response except in a few cases. The 1974 and the 1975 data show greater similarity in the responses of the individual varieties.

The varying response of a variety under different naturally occurring disease development conditions is greatly significant in the assessment of its resistance or susceptibility to bacterial leaf blight in similar environments.